

Research Methodology in Computing

Research Design

“Design a controlled experiment and State of the practice survey”

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Part1–Experiment design

1.Background/Introduction

From the web application security, I selected two tools (from <https://owasp.org/www-project-top-ten/>).

- **Tool A (A01:2021 - Broken Access Control)**
- **Tool B (A03:2021 - Injection)**

Tool	Description	Functionality	Popularity
Tool A (A01:2021 - Broken Access Control)	Broken Access Control is an important vulnerability identified by the OWASP Top 10 list. This vulnerability occurs when users are able to access unauthorized resources or perform actions beyond their intended privileges. So as a result, sensitive data exposure, privilege	Security tool for web applications to detect and prevent broken access by ensuring proper access control mechanisms are enforced throughout the application.	94% of applications were tested for some form of broken access control. The 34 Common Weakness Enumerations (CWEs) mapped to Broken Access Control had more occurrences in applications than any other category.

	escalation, or system are under		
Tool B (A03:2021 - Injection):	<p>Injection is a type of vulnerability where malicious data is sent to the translator as part of a query or command. Common types of injection vulnerabilities include SQL injection and Cross-Site Scripting (XSS). Injection vulnerabilities can lead to unauthorized access to data or complete compromise of the application. Detection tools aim to identify places where un validated or un sanitized input can be exploited.</p>	<p>This tool aim to identify places where un validated or un sanitized input can be exploited</p>	<p>94% of the applications were tested for some form of injection, and the 33 CWEs mapped into this category have the second most occurrences in applications. Cross-site Scripting is now part of this category in this edition</p>

2. Scoping

A01:2021 - Broken Access Control and A03:2021 - Injection to find the scope of their effectiveness in detecting broken access control and injection vulnerabilities.

We Should consider the following:

Tool performance with respect to their detection accuracy from the point of view of security testers and developers for a real-world web application project.

3. Hypothesis Formulation

Null Hypothesis: There is no major difference in the performance of the tools detecting broken access control and injection vulnerabilities in web applications.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a major difference in the performance of the tools detecting broken access control and injection vulnerabilities in web applications.

4. Variable Selection

Independent Variable: The vulnerability types being evaluated (broken access control and injection).

Dependent Variable: The performance of the tools, measured by the number of vulnerabilities detected (broken access control and injection vulnerabilities).

5. Experiment Design Type and Description

This experiment will be designed for the One factor with two treatments design.

- The factor is the vulnerability type detected.
- The treatments are **broken access control** and **injection vulnerabilities**.

Both tools will be tested on a web application project having known broken access control and injection vulnerabilities.

6. Instrumentation

For the answer the research questions, it is necessary to

1. Find the tools, performance measuring criteria for the tools for detection of security vulnerabilities in web based applications.
2. Find the limitations and strengths of current tools for detecting security vulnerabilities in web-based applications.

7. Threats and Mitigation Strategies

Internal Validity Threats: Changes in the setup of the vulnerability detection tools could give unexpected results. To mitigate this, try to have similar setup and configurations for both tests of broken access control and injection vulnerabilities.

External Validity Threats: The results can not be applied to all projects. So it should be clear that what vulnerabilities can be in the specific project.

Construct Validity Threats: The tools can cover on different vulnerability categories. The experiment will focus on common vulnerability types shared by both tools for a valid comparison.

Part 2- State of the Practice Survey

1. Informed Consent

Dear Survey Participant,

The purpose of survey :

The purpose of this survey is to understand the tools being used, their effectiveness, and the challenges users face.

You will participate voluntary. The survey will not take more than 5 minutes. The collected data will be anonymous and used solely for academic purposes. Your responses will remain confidential, and only aggregated data will be shared.

Outcome of this survey:

This survey will result to collect facts and figures for the current practices of using security vulnerability detection tools in web applications and API projects

2. Questionnaire– Demographics

If you agree to participate, please proceed by answering the questions below.

I agree to participate in the survey Yes No

1. What is your role in the organization?

(a) Developer (b) Tester (c) Security Analyst (d) Manager

2 How many years of experience do you have in software development or testing?

- (a) Less than 1 year (b)1-3 year (c) 4-6 years (d)More than 6 years

3.What is the size of your organization?

- (a) Small (b) Medium (c) Large

4.What industry does your organization belong to?

- (a) Finance (b) healthcare (c) E –commerce (d)Other

5.Which platforms do you mainly work on?

- (a)Web (b)Cloud (c)Mobile (d) Desktop

3. Questionnaire– Main

- Which security vulnerability detection tools do you use regularly? (Select all that apply)

- (a) Burp Suit (b) SonarQube (c)OWASP ZAP (d)any other

- How often do you use these tools in your development lifecycle?

- (a) Daily (b) Weekly (c) Monthly (d)Some times

- How effective are these tools in detecting security vulnerabilities in your projects?

(5 means more effective and 1 mean less)

- (a) 5 (b) 4(c)3 (d)2 (e)1

- What types of vulnerabilities are most commonly detected by these tools in your projects?
 - (a) Broken Access Control (b) Injection(SQL ,XSS) (C) Insecure Authentication (d)Other
 - What challenges do you face when using these tools? (Open-ended)

References:

Calvi, A., & Viganò, L. (2016). An automated approach for testing the security of web applications against chained attacks. In Proceedings of the 31st Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing (pp. 2095–2102).

<https://owasp.org/www-project-top-ten>

<https://owasp.org/www-project-apisecurity/>

<https://owasp.org/www-project-mobile-top-10/>